

ATTITUDE OF TEACHER TOWARDS WORKSHOP AND SEMINAR

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Objective:

- To find out the Attitude of teachers towards workshop and Seminar.
- To study the Attitude of teachers toward workshop and seminar in relation to Aided and Non-Aided school.

Hypothesis:

There is significant difference between Aided and Non aided teachers of secondary schools with respect to their attitude towards workshop and seminar.

Design of the Study

The design of the study is a descriptive survey which attempts to collect data from members of a population in order to determine the current status of the population.

Sample And Sampling Techniques

The sample consisted of 120 teachers from aided and non aided schools in Mumbai. The schools are selected by simple random technique.

Tools for Data Collection

A questionnaire was used with a three-points rating scale in order to collect the views of teachers about the Attitude towards workshop and seminar. The tool used for data collection consisted of 16 items which is developed by the researcher and validated by experts.

Procedure of the Study:

In order to get data from the respondents with the help of a tool, the researcher visited the sample schools personally and administered the questionnaires to the sample teachers. The respondents were requested to record their free, frank and independent responses. An assurance was given to the respondents that their responses shall be kept confidential and information collected will be used only for the purpose for which it is collected. The collected data was analyzed by using percentage; mean, SD, T-test.

Table1- Responses of Teachers

Sr	Statements		Agree	undecided	Disagree
1	Have you attend any seminar and workshop.	Response	52	-	08
		Percentage	86.6	-	13.4
2	Do you find them useful?	Response	53	4	3
		Percentage	88.3	6.6	5.1
3	Should these training be held regularly?	Response	52	3	5
		Percentage	86.6	5.1	8.3
4	Does the training have any impact on the student?	Response	45	8	7
		Percentage	75	13.3	11.6
5	Do you need training in any subject?	Response	48	6	6
		Percentage	80	10	10

6	Do you find any change in your skills/technique?	Response	50	4	6
		Percentage	83.3	6.6	10
7	Do you find any gain in any knowledge, subject matter?	Response	52	2	6
		Percentage	86.6	3.3	10
8	Do you refer library books?	Response	47	3	10
		Percentage	78.3	5.1	16
9	Do you share the knowledge of seminar /workshop?	Response	55	1	4
		Percentage	91.6	1.6	6.6
10	Does your head of institution send you regularly for the training?	Response	50	2	8
		Percentage	83.3	3.3	13.4
11	Do you think there is any other alternate for the training?	Response	42	6	12
		Percentage	70	10	20.2
12	Is hand book is sufficient for proper guidance?	Response	52	3	5
		Percentage	86.6	5.1	8.3
13	Have you ever arrange any workshop/seminar?	Response	42	6	10
		Percentage	70	10	16
14	Was the response of seminar is positive?	Response	35	8	17
		Percentage	58.3	13.4	28.3
15	Does the headmaster appreciate your teaching after attending the seminar and workshop?	Response	44	5	11
		Percentage	73.3	8.3	18.3
16	Do you think training centre should be nearest to school?	Response	54	2	4
		Percentage	90	3.3	6.6

Table2- Showing the test of significance of difference between the Mean score of Aided and non Aided school teachers

Sr. NO	Teacher's Attitude	N	Mean	S.D	CR	Sig/insignificant
1	Aided	60	59.12	6.4	0.97	Significant at 0.05 level
2	Non-Aided	60	57.08	7.1		

Results

- In this study one of the objectives was to determine the percentage of teachers attitude towards workshop and seminar, data illustrate that 88% of teachers attitude towards seminar and workshop was that it is useful for improving their teaching skills and techniques.
- 91.6% of teachers opined that, they share the knowledge of seminar and workshop to their colleagues.
- 90% of teachers opined that training centres should be nearest to schools otherwise school should provide travelling facility to the training centre.

- 83% of teachers attained the workshop and seminar from aided school because it is a norm for the teachers to participate. On the contrary only 35% of the teachers belonging to non-aided schools are allowed to participate.
- 75% of teacher thinks that training have an impact on the students.

Testing of Hypothesis:

The significant difference between the Attitude of aided and non aided high school teachers is accepted because Mean scores of aided teachers is greater than non aided and table-2 reveal that t-value is 0.97 which is less than the table value 1.98 at both the level of significance(df=118) hence differences of Mean is significant. It could be inferred that aided & non aided school teachers differ with attitude towards attending of workshop and seminar.

DISCUSSION:

The summary Table 1 shows that in the opinions of teachers 13 items were accepted out of 16 and only 3 items were rejected. It means that the generally Attitude of teachers was positive towards workshop and seminar.

The majority of teachers agreed that the teachers used different motivational techniques, different teaching techniques to make teaching effective after attending the workshop and seminar. Finally, this study shows that Attitude of school teachers of Mumbai have been found favorable towards the workshop and seminar.